

The fall of bodies, the gravitational self energy and the Schwarzschild radius as the boundary of the unattainable region

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Abstract

The fundamental role of self energy in the reinterpretation of the Schwarzschild radius is underlined. In close analogy with the classical radius of the electron the Schwarzschild radius is seen to define the unattainable region, thus eliminating the problem of the singularity of gravitation. The simplicity and the physical foundations of an alternative elementary derivation of General Relativity results based on the Equivalence Principle and Special Relativity is reasserted.

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1 The fall of bodies and the Schwarzschild radius

The Newtonian law [1] of falling bodies under the attraction of a mass M is the well known

$$v^2(r) = 2GM/r \quad (1)$$

v standing for the velocity of a falling mass at a distance r from M. Such a law has been extended in General Relativity (GR) [2] and the most popular solution for non rotating objects is represented by the Schwarzschild (S) [3] metric. A particularly transparent formulation is provided in the Painlevé [4] Gullstrand [5] (P-G) alternative metric where this law represents the velocity of the free falling frame (FFF) in which light can be emitted isotropically. Given the law, fall can be used to get information on the source. Indeed if the falling body reaches the velocity c , the features of the source must be such that

$$\frac{2GM}{c^2 R} = 1 \quad (2)$$

This defines a black hole (BH) and represents the strong field limit of gravitation.

An independent piece of information, which confirms the previous result, comes from the consideration of gravitational self energy. Consider indeed a mass M whose energy under the effect of gravity is

$$E = Mc^2 - \frac{GM^2}{R} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where the first term comes from the sum of the masses of its constituents and the second term represents the order of magnitude of its self-energy, coming from the work necessary to assemble them from infinity. The negative contribution of the self energy, is well known and forbids, because of its repulsive character, to accumulate an infinite amount of matter. This can be seen in Fig.1) where the energy E is plotted as a function of M ; it is zero of course if no matter is present and also at

$$M_{max} \simeq \frac{c^2}{G} R_S = M_S \quad (4)$$

R_S standing for the Schwarzschild radius , where the self energy completely balances the total mass. The sign (\simeq) appears because of an unknown numerical factor depending on the matter distribution in front of the self energy.

Figure 1: Energy of a composite object of total mass M , sum of masses m , as a function of M for given radius R without self energy (straight line) and with (curved line) The second intercepts happens at the Schwarzschild mass.

Thus *the masses obtained from the fall law and self energy considerations are the same up to numerical coefficients* and a BH corresponds to the situation where matter reaches the strong limit (maximum mass assembly) allowed by self energy (with a warning also about the validity of the extrapolation of Newtonian dynamics to such extreme conditions).

Consider gravitation in the P-G metric. It describes relativistic gravitation as a sequel of free falling inertial frames with the Newtonian velocity where light is emitted according to Special Relativity. Photon emission is obtained by properly setting to zero the invariant interval

$$ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - (dr - v(r)dt)^2 - dr_{\perp}^2 = c^2(1 - v^2(r)/c^2)dt^2 + 2v(r)dt dr - dr^2 - dr_{\perp}^2 \quad (5)$$

yielding

$$dr/dt = c(\pm 1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}) \quad (6)$$

Thus photons cannot be emitted ($c = 1$) if the source obeys the Schwarzschild condition ($\frac{2GM}{c^2 r} = 1$). This provides an elementary justification of the Michell and Laplace argument (BH does not let even light to escape) without having to invoke mysterious GR effects. The huge attraction is not due to a space funnel-like deformation [6] which becomes singular at the BH radius, proper to the Schwarzschild metric, since in the P-G metric space is euclidean, but to the fact that the mass can reach smaller distances ($\frac{1}{R_S} \gg \frac{1}{R_{ord}}$), with respect to the dimensions of the source in ordinary conditions (i.e. objects very far from the strong field limit).

A totally similar treatment with the same approximations is used to derive the classical radius of the electron. [7]¹

The analogy of the Schwarzschild radius with the classical electron radius is manifest: in a sense it represents a classical gravitational radius. With the essential difference that it is not universal but varies according

¹It is also obtained by imposing that its electrostatic energy cancels its relativistic energy

$$m_e c^2 - \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_o} = 0 \quad (7)$$

whence one obtains r_o .

to the amount of mass in question. *Most relevant it removes classically the gravitation singularity since it forbids the possibility of reaching the origin.* ($v > c$) Thus all speculations about the inside of a BH are idle. That corrects previous results [6].

2 Gravitation in the Lagrangian formulation

Let us now consider the alternative P-G derivation of the relativistic treatment of gravitation. Its dynamical ingredient is just Newton's law and therefore very far from the strong field limit. Indeed the three tests of GR are dependent on the parameter $\frac{GM}{c^2 r} \simeq 10^{-6}$.

a) Newton's law

The impact Special Relativity (SR) [8] has had on our picture of the world can be hardly underestimated. However its message, to give a meaning to measurable quantities only, has been somewhat lost in General Relativity (GR) due to the existence of different metrics, not always directly connected to measurable time and space intervals. For this reason reconsider the P-G metric and discuss its physical basis, obtained independently of GR but based on the same original idea of Einstein that gravitation can be locally eliminated in the free fall frame (FFF) which represents therefore an equivalence principle (EP) inertial frame (EPIF). Therefore in these frames, which fall according to **Newton's law** in terms of an **absolute time** in a euclidean space, SR is manifestly valid. The only problem resides in relating the infinitesimal displacement in the local system to that in external (global) coordinates. This implies an analogous relation for velocities.

Classical Mechanics can be formulated in terms of the principle of least action in inertial frames. The implementation of the EP in the non relativistic free Lagrangian $\mathcal{L} = m/2 \dot{r}^2$ is immediate. It is enough to express the velocity in the local EPIF or in other words to subtract the free fall velocity

$$\dot{r} \rightarrow \dot{r} - v(r)$$

The principle of least action for a particle in the presence of gravity is thus given by

$$\delta \int dt (m/2 [(\dot{r} - v(r))^2 + r^2(\dot{\theta})^2]) = 0. \quad (8)$$

The Lagrange equations yield for the radial coordinate

$$\begin{aligned} d/dt(\dot{r} - v(r)) + (\dot{r} - v(r))dv/dr - r(\dot{\theta})^2 = \\ = \ddot{r} - d/dr(1/2v^2(r)) - r(\dot{\theta})^2 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Since $1/2 v^2(r) = GM/r$, the Newton's radial equation of motion is obtained

$$\ddot{r} = -GM/r^2 \quad (10)$$

and analogous equation can be derived also for the angular variables. A constant v would only amount to a change of inertial frame. Let us stress how closely related are the EP and the equation of motion.

e) Relativistic Newton's law

The relativistic extension of the previous result is easily obtained in the same Lagrangian approach. The formulation of relativistic mechanics is immediate via the EP, which only amounts to substitute stationarity of the Minkowski invariant interval in inertial frames with the same for invariant intervals in EPIFs. The corresponding action is therefore obtained, as in the non-relativistic case, by the substitution $\dot{r} \rightarrow \dot{r} - v(r)$

$$\delta A = \delta \int \mathcal{L} dt = \delta \int ds = \delta \int dt (mc^2) \sqrt{(1 - 1/c^2[(\dot{r} - v(r))^2 + r^2(\dot{\theta})^2])} = 0 \quad (11)$$

The equation of motion are given by the corresponding Euler Lagrange equations [9] [10].² They are equivalent to the geodesic equations in the metric defined by the above invariant interval, i.e. in the P-G metric.

Both solve in fact the same variational problem, the ordinary geodesic equations being obtained from a parametrization of trajectories with the proper time. Let us also mention that the use of proper times is inappropriate in the many body case, which implies that relativistic Newtonian gravitation is non linear as GR. Let us recall that the same principle of the variation of the action was used by Hilbert [11] for the alternative derivation of Einstein's equations.

Thus

$$\mathcal{L} = (mc^2) \sqrt{(1 - 1/c^2[(\dot{r} - v(r))^2 + r^2(\dot{\theta})^2])} \equiv G_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (12)$$

where in the final equation $T_{\mu\nu}$ represents the well known energy momentum tensor and $G_{\mu\nu}$ the metric tensor which is said to contain all the geometric and causal structure of spacetime.

Thus *the Lagrangian formulation is equivalent to the much more involved GR formulation since the "fundamental tests" of GR have been obtained [9] [10] equally well from the relativistic Newtonian Lagrangian in euclidean space.* It is clear from the way these equations have been derived that the fundamental role is played just by Newton's law, its relativistic corrections being trivially expressed in terms of the weak field parameter $\frac{GM}{c^2 r} = \epsilon$. Their exact and a bit complicated expression in terms of ϵ is crucial *only* for the calculation of Mercury's perihelion (the other two "fundamental tests" being reproduced even without GR). This parameter is obviously unrelated to the corresponding quantity which governs the Universe (U) $\frac{GM_U}{c^2 R_U} = 1$ [12].

In relations to Eq.(12) one might wonder why the tensor structure of GR is absent in the Lagrangian formulation. This is due to the fact

²A misprint appears in Eq.(15) of that reference The correct equation is the above one.

that the S metric is diagonal, unlike the P-G one where a crossed term coming from the EP is present. The S metric implies space funnel-like deformations which in turn require affine connections to "relate deformed space to euclidean one". How both possibilities are present in GR equations is discussed in [13]. A further remark about the fact that GR be "the" theory of gravitation. In the neglected paper by Feynman the said formulation based on a tensor description of gravitation mediated by a graviton reproduces both radiation and the factor of 2 in the deflection of light. Thus one sees that alternative formulations are legitimate.

Let us also stress that the apparent instantaneous feature of Newton's law has been shown in the beautiful approach by Feynman [14] to result as a low energy limit of a relativistic treatment based on the energy conserving amplitude for the exchange of a graviton between energy momentum tensors. This parallels the analogous treatment by Fermi [15] for the Coulomb potential.

3 Conclusions: much ado about .. ?

The aim of the present paper has been to try to clarify the nature of mysterious black holes. They have been connected to the inherent repulsive effect of gravitational self energy, thus defining, in analogy with the classical radius of the electron, the unattainable region for gravitation. This cures at the same time the singularity of gravitation. In addition wide spread misbeliefs about the reality of space deformation and the necessity of the accompanying mathematical complications of GR have been countered.³ It has been shown that the same results can be obtained in a much simpler and more physically founded formalism, supporting the physical content of the P-G metric over the S one. Thus in a sense in the description of reality, SR has regained its fundamental role with respect to GR, the dynamics being essentially given just from relativistic corrections to Newton's law.

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³Thus the phrase by Wheeler "Matter tells space how to curve. Space tells matter how to move" represents just an appealing interpretation of GR equations, without physical reality. It has to be replaced by the humbler "in undistorted space just relativistic Newtonian dynamics does the job".

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